

The Nansen Legacy

With a focus on the seasonally ice-covered northern Barents Sea and adjacent waters, Norway established a national team of complementary disciplinary and institutional competence and approaches. The Nansen Legacy project constitute a more holistic research platform to meet the complex research questions and knowledge needs that follows rapid climate change and increased accessibility of Arctic marine waters. After six years, the unique project has proved to be successful on many levels including science, collaboration and education of a new generation of polar researchers.

ONE PROJECT

>10 FIELDS OF RESEARCH
>300 SCIENTISTS

to understand

ONE OCEAN

Achievements

The project work/team ...

... strengthened the scientific collaboration across Norway and internationally, resulting in complementary research across temporal and spatial scales that contributes to a more holistic understanding of the marine Arctic, drivers and responses.

... established scientific knowledge on the northern Barents Sea climate- and ecosystem as basis for sustainable management beyond the present sea ice edge.

... characterized the main human- and natural influences/drivers on the changing ecosystems and their response – in past, present, and future.

... resolved the mechanisms governing the Barents Sea ice cover and climate state, including predictive capability.

... optimized use of emerging technologies, logistic capabilities, data handling, research recruitment and stakeholder interactions to explore and manage the emerging Arctic Ocean.

